

Using Benchmarking Data to Inform Decisions Related to Machine Learning Resource Efficiency

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Abstract

Machine Learning (ML) training and inference consume a considerable amount of resources that translate into high energy consumption. Amidst a backdrop of environmental pressure, it is imperative to utilize resources wisely to make computation more energy efficient - whether for on-prem HPC clusters or commercial cloud. This work focuses on studying speed and energy consumption of the MLCommons benchmarks. MLCommons sponsors benchmarking experiments and makes the results available, across a range of ML use cases and systems. Data quality of the benchmark results is also examined and assessed using the FAIR Principles. Our study shows that, by improving the way ML performance and system artifacts are created, stored, and shared, computer scientists and cyberinfrastructure professionals can enable the use of ML benchmarks to improve computation and energy efficiency. Further, our study proposes using energy traces to create “power consumption fingerprints” whereby application mismatches with underlying hardware can be detected.

INTRODUCTION

Benchmarking activities provide an opportunity to compare the same data and machine learning (ML) model runs on various hardware CPUs, accelerators, and software. This paper presents the results from analysis of MLCommons data for the comparison of ML models’ energy efficiency. An underexplored research area is to study benchmarks in order to improve performance and overall workload efficiency of ML’s compute tasks in a clear contrast to the traditional performance engineering methods (Boeme et al., 2016; Petkov et al., 2014). Potential benefits could range from new hardware and software combination recommendations to predicting job failure. Analyzing benchmark results can also help assess power consumption, cost, and relative efficiency of hardware and software options. Additionally, there are opportunities for validation and otherwise improving the quality of benchmarking results data that would allow for more rapid interpretation and visualization of insights.

Actions that result in improved benchmarking results data can be disseminated and adopted through the MLCommons community, by other benchmarking activities, and in related fields. However, the ability to mine these and similar data types is limited by a lack of standards for system profiling and performance logging.

This work is organized as follows. The first section provides background information about different approaches and relevant benchmarks for the comparison of computational systems' power consumption, as well as known limitations of measurement. Section two describes findings about energy consumption using ML analyses using data and tools made available by MLCommons Science. Additional detail using the CloudMask benchmark utilizing the CloudMesh toolkit is discussed. Section three provides insights from the data analysis process, including limitations of the current benchmark results and suggestions for improving the data through extended tools and research data management techniques.

BACKGROUND

The High Performance Computing (HPC) community has used benchmarking for decades. The most visible contest is the TOP500, which has been providing a ranking of the world's most powerful supercomputers since 1993. Systems run the HPL (High Performance LINPACK) benchmark, and results are verified by the TOP500 organization. This approach has been extended to highlight other priorities, such as the Green500 that ranks the TOP500 HPC systems according to energy efficiency. The Green500 ranking metric is performance- or gigaflops-per-watt. In recent results, the supercomputers ranked #187 and #128 are the most green TOP500 computers when power efficiency is included for 2024 (TOP500.org, 2024). Power monitoring is not built into the Green500's reported metric but one of three levels of power measurement and are required for the system to be accepted to the list, easing the ability of entrants to the benchmark. A limitation with the TOP500 is the use of HPL and the primary source of floating-point operations is the double precision general matrix-matrix multiplication (or BLAS routine called DGEMM), which is rarely used directly in ML, which prefers lower precision operations. Hence, the metric is not a good measure of value for ML system performance and a reason for the establishment of the MLCommons benchmarks. Recent metrics such as the HPL-MxP (formerly, HPL-AI) assess system performance in total mixed-precision FLOPS, but as in HPL, the computation is a dense matrix solver operation which is not representative of typical ML workflows. By contrast, commercial cloud users do not tend to contribute to system optimization through benchmarks, perhaps in part because inspection and reconfiguration of the underlying hardware is limited.

Energy Consumption of Computing Loads

Estimates put energy consumption of data centers at 1-1.5% of all energy consumed worldwide, and artificial intelligence (AI) could increase data center power demand by 160% (Rozite et al., 2024; Goldman Sachs, 2024). With energy demand outpacing supply, as well as climate pressures to increase energy efficiency, energy consumption in computing should be an urgent topic. HPC loads represent the greatest energy consumption by computing equipment type. In the data center at the San Diego Supercomputer Center (SDSC), an average 42-48u rack of storage equipment draws around 7kW, whereas even the simplest compute cluster draws 25 kW per rack on the low end, with some racks needing 140kW per rack.¹ HPC racks of US National Science Foundation funded systems have been so hot and energy dense, that even commodity nodes when racked together are requiring alternatives to

¹ Based on interviews with Thomas Tate, Brian Balderston San Diego Supercomputer Center, 2022, 2024.

air cooling with ranges between 30kW - 45kW/rack for direct to liquid (DLC) cooled chip installations. In the near term, SDSC is installing new racks to accommodate up to 160kW - 200kW per rack, primarily to meet demand of dedicated AI systems. The need for more efficient cooling technologies has led to the ARPA-E COOLERCHIPS program which targets a reduction in total cooling energy expenditure to less than 5% of a typical data center's IT load at any time and any U.S. location for a high-density compute system.

It is difficult to estimate power consumption of ML processes as the power consumption of each processor and accelerator fluctuates during actual use and varies based on software settings (see the "Resource Utilization Example" further down). One investigative report of supercomputing centers showed fluctuations in the compute nodes of HPC clusters during benchmarking by as much as 2 megawatts (MW) in time periods of less than one second; optimized numerical simulation portions of the benchmark drew 3 MW versus only 1 MW during MPI-I/O phases (Prisco et al., 2020).

Primer

Analysis of processor power consumption is challenging due to the lack of universal power consumption specifications. Focusing only on the processors and accelerators allows for relative comparison of systems and energy loads. Manufacturers aren't required to disclose uniform power consumption specifications. AMD offers its own metric: the Average CPU power (ACP), which is the average power dissipated when running computation. Critics maintain that ACPs' estimates are too low (De Gelas, 2009; Huck, 2011).

The closest measure available to assess power consumption of processors is the Thermal Design Power (TDP) measurement. TDP reports the thermal solution needed to dissipate heat loads and is used by manufacturers of motherboards to understand the power requirements of processors. It is not designed for gauging energy efficiency or costs, but rather the worst-case maximum heat. Even so, sources show that the TDP is the maximum at steady state, but not the actual "maximum instantaneous power" that may need to be cooled; thus actual heat load can be much higher (Ganapathy & Warner, 2008). Furthermore, TDP is often reported as a range, which complicates factoring it into power estimates. The greatest limitation of TDP is that it only describes the processor and not the entire system it is plugged into. Nevertheless, it allows for comparison of computational resources' energy properties and insight into the tradeoffs between different systems.

Node Power Consumption

Whole methodologies exist for measuring computational energy consumption, as well as proper sampling models to extrapolate the energy usage profile of a large HPC system. Notable work has been published by the Energy Efficiency High Performance Computing Working Group (EE HPC WG), who designed the Power API to employ suggested practices.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The MLCommons consortium began in 2018 with MLPerf benchmarks. The aim is to drive improvements in ML through sharing of performance data using established benchmarks (Thiyagalingam et al., 2022; MLCommons, n.d.a). The consortium has profiled systems such as commodity hardware readily available for purchase, and proprietary and specialized hardware in the commercial cloud, whose relative performance would not otherwise be known to the larger ML community. The benchmarks have expanded into eight types (see Supplementary Material). The analysis discussed here focuses on the image classification benchmark in "Training" and one of the classification benchmarks for "Science."

MLCommons benchmark results provide data that can be mined for insights and an opportunity to include power consumption data with results. As with the Green500, this would allow observations to

be a balance of computational efficiency and power consumption. In recent benchmark rounds for MLPerf Inference (3.0) and Mobile (3.0), many submissions included accelerators' TDP values.

MLCommons benchmark data includes a summary table of results shared on the MLCommons website, as well as corresponding log files with benchmark data stored as text files, and system profiles in JSON. Each entry includes up to five results per submission for a particular machine or cluster. The results are stored as files with an organized directory structure on the MLCommons GitHub (MLCommons, n.d.b).

Limitations of Measurement

Using TDP or other self-reported manufacturer specifications is limiting where those specifications have not been disclosed. In the case of MLCommons benchmarks and the various systems used by those submitting benchmarks, some utilize proprietary processors where the specifications are not available (e.g., the Graphcore IPU GC200's TDP). Specifications are unverifiable in some cases. Google does not publish specifications for its TPUs, as compared to NVIDIA or AMD (Google Cloud, 2024; NVIDIA, 2021; Prickett Morgan, 2024). Google's self-reported analysis claims that the TPU v4 is 1.3-1.9 times more energy efficient than the NVIDIA A100 (Jouppi et al., 2023). Using the NVIDIA's published TDP for the A100, one can estimate that the TPU's TDP is 280W. The lower multiplier (1.3x) is consistent with the typical range of other accelerators in the v1.1 Training benchmark submissions range that fall between 140-280W.

Resource Utilization Example

Thanks to the progress of chip manufacturing, AI accelerators have achieved Tera and Petaflop scale. However, this is "theoretical peak performance," which refers to the physical limit that a device can achieve, provided that the application is fine-tuned to match the architecture of the chip. Though power consumption between accelerators and systems is useful for comparison's sake, consumption is not constant but comes in bursts based on the operations the chip is handling. Furthermore, applications rarely take the full advantage of the full performance potential due to the mismatch between the applications' workload characteristics and the underlying hardware. On the level of processing elements and memory, the growing gap between the speed of processing and data access has become the key factor impacting performance. Consequently, the cost of delivering data along with power consumption have become the targets of chip design optimization.

In order to gain some idea about the interaction between the application and the hardware, profiling information must be collected. There are many profiling tools that collect large volumes of detailed information. However, the increasing amount of data limits the duration of the monitoring period, and making sense of the fine grain details can also be a challenge. To resolve this dilemma, a simple sampling technique which reads the status of the computing device in regular intervals and summarizes the data by histograms provides an easy visualization of power consumption. The amount of collected data is minimal, allowing long-term monitoring. The histograms provide a high-level view of resource utilization, power consumption and temperature variation. These histograms can be considered as a "fingerprint" which provides a quantitative measure of how well an application matches the underlying hardware. They are generated using the CloudMesh library used by the CloudMask benchmark. In the example below (Figure 1), the CloudMask benchmark that uses image classification to identify clouds in satellite imagery is profiled.

FIGURE 1. GPU utilization of CloudMask benchmark

Traditionally, runtime has been the main concern of performance studies, with power consumption historically being paid less attention. However, this attitude has changed recently, and it is no longer sufficient to run simulations or analyses quickly, but also with the smallest amount of power. The “power consumption fingerprint” of the CloudMask benchmark is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The power drawn by the CloudMask benchmark

Figure 2 illustrates differing utilization and power consumption of GPUs during the ML processing. Understanding GPU utilization of differing compute architectures and software stacks could also lead to more efficient use of GPUs.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

With the above context in mind, a subset of MLCommons data was targeted for further analysis.

Accessing & Cleaning

The data was collected from multiple rounds of training benchmarks (v1.0, v1.1, and v3.0) with a focus on the ResNet benchmark because it had the most entries. ResNet refers to a residual neural network – a type of deep learning model – that was employed for image classification on the ImageNet dataset. The summary results table provided by MLCommons (MLCommons, n.d.c.) was amended with additional values and reviewed to match the benchmark results on GitHub. The metadata for the processor and accelerator TDP were added to the table where available (see Supplementary Materials).

Data Issues and Limitations

While the desire at the outset of this work was to use feature selection or similar ML techniques for further insight, the MLCommons ResNet benchmark results data is a relatively small dataset (36-80 submissions per round), and too small for ML inquiry. Within these small sets of records, the individual data quality is lacking and only a subset has the needed detail for further analysis.

Nonspecific Vocabulary & Quality

The MLCommons benchmark data's quality and specificity limits its use for further analysis. A Google submission lists the processor as "AMD ROME," of which there are two dozen types. In some cases, the processor can be deduced from other system attributes (e.g., the L2 cache). The system profiles contain typos and do not use a controlled vocabulary to constrain entries to valid software versions. Entries inaccurately document software versions. (e.g., "Dell 'Tensorflow 21.05'" which is a version of a specific NVIDIA container that includes Tensorflow) which limits reproducibility.

Data Validation and Provenance

Each submitted benchmark includes five runs, but uniform numbering is not enforced. Most submissions number these 1-5, but some label them 0-4. This discrepancy disrupts result comparisons between benchmark runs.

Too Much or Too Little Information

Different log verbosity setting choices can provide very different results and complicate analysis. For example, the submitted results ranged from text files with 100 lines to 30,000 lines, with 3,500 lines being most typical.

Opportunities for Improving MLCommons Benchmark Data Results

Several actions could be undertaken to improve the machine accessibility and ease analysis of the results (see Table 1).

FAIR Principle	Opportunities to implement FAIR
F1 (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier	Assign unique identifiers to results
A1 (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable	Results accessible via open API
I2 (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	(FAIR) vocabularies used
R1.2 (meta)data are associated with their provenance	Provenance included in results and not only derived from directory structure

Table 1. Summary of MLCommons Data Improvements by FAIR Principle

- **Format results in a more reusable format.** The results could be made available in an extensible format, csv or Google sheet, rather than an HTML table.
- **Extend CloudMesh capabilities.** Analyzing the HTML summary results requires scraping the data, an easy way to introduce errors. The CloudMesh tool allows for some of this capability and could be extended by MLCommons (von Laszewski et al., 2022). The CloudMesh stopwatch writes in parallel to mlog and can write out in any format needed (e.g., html, yaml, csv, json, txt, latex and mlog).

- **Use unique identifiers.** Assigning globally unique, persistent and resolvable identifiers (GUPRIs) to submissions, submitters, systems, and data used would aid in the accuracy of tracing results and analysis.
- **Create or extend controlled vocabularies and map to existing ontologies.** For example, identify or create a controlled vocabulary with a standardized listing of existing processors. An existing MLCommons working group could maintain the list and amend as new processors are released or used in benchmark submissions.
- **Include power consumption data.** This could take the form of the kW per node and the Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) of the host site's data center.
- **Enforce the submission directory structure or replace with metadata.** The submitter's directory structure substitutes for explicit metadata (e.g. the specific run tied to a specific submission). Enforcing directory structures would make scripted analysis easier. An additional improvement would be to add the implied Information from the directory structure as actual metadata within the submitted files.

MLCommons Benchmark Results Data

Two areas became the focus for analysis: relative efficiency of the ResNet and BERT benchmarks, and comparison of results in minutes as compared to power consumption. ResNet is a machine learning model for image classification. BERT is a machine learning model for natural language processing.

Relative Power Efficiency

The MLCommons Training and HPC-submitted results provide useful information on the compute performance as a function of system (accelerator) type and size.

ResNet	4	4	8	64	1024	3456	4096
A100	0.92	1	0.95	0.76	0.39		0.16
TPUv4						0.28	0.28
H100			1.86	1.52			
BERT on	4	4 SXM	8	64	1024	3456	4096
A100	0.72	1	0.99	0.84	0.31		0.16
TPUv4						0.17	0.18
H100			2.62	2.32			

Table 2. Scaled System Performance for the MLCommons 2022 Training Submissions for ResNet and BERT Benchmark

Table 2 presents submitted performance numbers as speedup efficiency defined as follows:

$$\frac{(Execution\ time\ 1) * (Number\ of\ nodes\ 1)}{(Execution\ time\ 2) * (Number\ of\ nodes\ 2)}$$

where reference System 1 is a 4-node A100 with SXM (a high bandwidth socket connecting the GPUs to the system) and System 2 runs over other submitted systems. The column labels the system characteristics, and the rows are different accelerators. In some cases, the number of nodes is different from the column value and then it is listed in parentheses in the cell.

The listed efficiency decreases as system size increases due to decreasing parallel efficiency (usually communication overhead). Numbers increase for H100 and TPUv4 accelerators as these are faster than the A100. The rapid efficiency decrease as the scale of the job and nodes used increases

translates into greater power inefficiency. Further, given the size of these two datasets, one would likely run with larger system sizes, not realizing that the decreased execution time comes at a greater power cost. Results with a larger choice of system sizes could allow a more informed choice of maximum useful size with a criterion such as the efficiency >0.5 . Larger models such as ChatGPT or Bard would run much better on large systems.

Training v1.0 and v3.0 Analysis for ResNet Benchmarks.

The goal was to illustrate the relative tradeoffs between different benchmarking results and the electricity consumed. Submission results were plotted by time and energy consumed in kilowatts. Where TDP was reported as a range, the lowest TDP was used. While the actual energy consumption of the results varies widely and is unknown, these hypothetical consumption estimates are built from the most energy intensive hardware component consumption specifications and allow one to contemplate the consumption tradeoffs. Another way to put the consumption into perspective is to calculate the power cost. Electricity rates and price tiers vary by region and utility provider, and can be very complex. Even though the monetary cost of a benchmark proved compelling in some cases, it includes too many additional variables and sensitivities, especially for advanced computing centers that rely on their institutions to pay for power via overhead (indirect cost recovery) collected from contracts and grants. For these reasons, the focus of the analysis is on kW consumed.

Outliers

The experiments that did not use accelerators nor other outliers made it difficult to see patterns in the majority of the data, but were also a source of important inquiry. Of the complete benchmarks where costs could be discerned, less than 10% of them consumed more than 20 kW. For example, an Intel submission that used 8 Intel Xenon Platinum CPUs and no GPUs took ~16 hours and consumed 314 kW.

The highest consumption benchmark was the third fastest (NVIDIA: 629 kW for .4 minutes using 620 AMD EPYC 7742 and 2,400 NVIDIA A100s). By contrast, the second fastest time used 40% less energy: Google at 369 kW for .28 minutes using 1,024 AMD Rome CPUs and 2,048 TPUs. Using the same CPUs and TPUs, Google had the fastest benchmark (619 kW for .23 minutes using 1,728 AMD Rome CPUs and 3,456 TPUs). Reviewing Google's two best benchmarks illustrates that adding more computational power does not always scale linearly. Further, unless the use case requires speed at any cost, occupying the additional 1,408 TPUs (or 1.45 times more accelerators) for not much performance gain (.05 seconds or less than 20% faster) is not the best use of finite resources.

For this reason, we reran the analysis after excluding the outliers. This allowed for closer examination of the results with relative power consumption below 8kW. Plotting benchmarks in minutes-by-kilowatts-of-energy-consumed helps illustrate the inefficiency in time and electricity consumption for running ML image classification processes without GPUs or other accelerators. Our experiments uncovered that benchmarks without GPUs take three times as long to run and consume and are at the high end for electricity consumption across all submissions. In other words, ML computation without accelerators occupies nodes better utilized for other tasks. The slowest GPU configuration from Fujitsu was almost four times as fast as the quickest CPU-only benchmark result from Intel.

The same analysis was conducted with the Training v3.0 benchmarks — once again, excluding outliers. The two fastest benchmarks were from Google, with the fastest (at .23 minutes) consuming 1.67 times the electricity of the runner-up (at .28 minutes). Another fast NVIDIA benchmark at 4.91 minutes and 18.95 kW using NVIDIA A100 GPUs outperformed the Dell submission using NVIDIA A100s with half the cache at 15.5 minutes and only 6.6 kW. Our analysis suggested a relative lower electricity consumption of the NVIDIA A100-PCIE-40GB accelerator in concert with PyTorch and

Tensorflow optimized for this particular GPU than compared with other hardware and software combinations.

Information about energy consumption over speed can be valuable for different AI use cases and contexts. In healthcare, air traffic control, or military applications, speed may be the priority at any cost. However, many research applications may have no perceived benefit to quicker processing. Where consumers bear the costs, they may opt for the cheapest utility costs.

Some of the lowest energy consumption benchmark results don't use novel hardware configurations. For example, in Training v3.0 on ResNet, NVIDIA has one of the fastest results, but for the highest power consumption: 0.369 mins for 632 kW. When a modest amount of GPUs is used (8 vs. 768 H100s) and CPUS (2 vs. 192 Xeon Platinum 8480C), it is both fast and energy efficient: 13.601 minutes for 8.4 kW. For ~96 times the GPUs, the NVIDIA result is only ~37 times as fast. In other words, the benchmark improvement is not linear given the additional resources used. This can be due to a variety of factors including how many floating point operations are invoked, data copy times and the type of interconnect used.

Energy Tracing with the Earthquake Science Application Using CloudMesh

Comparing computation time with energy consumption is useful for the reasons illuminated above, but it does not give the complete picture of electricity usage. During computation, energy fluctuates, sometimes significantly. To understand this, we examined one of the key MLCommons Science benchmarks: CloudMesh.

CloudMesh was developed with tools in mind that ease the capturing of energy traces from applications obtained with various hyperparameters. The code for energy monitoring capabilities of NVIDIA GPUs was leveraged and the framework could be expanded to use other energy parameters.

This paper's co-author, von Laszewski, developed the following capabilities of CloudMesh for the purpose of MLCommons Science:

- The ability to augment a code with stopwatch timers and events that are available in human readable format and in mllog log files.
- A simple-to-use logging program that can be run parallel to the execution of the main program to be benchmarked, creating logging events at predefined times. The logging program utilizes the built-in NVIDIA logging capabilities. We augmented the program to generate visualizations from the logs, including log traces for earthquake prediction (see Figure 3) and histograms (see Figures 1-2).
- A framework to create workflows that allows for them to be applied to various HPC systems with a variety of GPUs. This enables comparisons between said workflows while guaranteeing the reproducibility of the experiments by considering variations in hardware configurations.
- The storage of energy traces that are in a separate file in csv format and can be submitted as part of the benchmark submission process. If needed, an mllog based format could also be created, but the current CloudMesh common format is useful as each energy event is much smaller than events created by mllog.

Using these capabilities, we uncovered that CloudMesh vacillates between 50W and 200W, depending on the point in the computation (see Figure 3). With this, we demonstrate that, on one HPC system, the filesystem performance could be significantly improved, leading both to a better performance and to a significant energy reduction.

Figure 3. An energy trace for the MLCommons Earthquake forecasting application. Energy traces can be helpful in identifying different phases of the algorithms. Here, the phases to conduct initialization are distinguished: training, validation (e.g., best fit prediction), and visualization of the results. Such phases can then be further analyzed in order to optimize access to filesystem or network resources as they may project a bottleneck in the available hardware and result in not optimized performance.

CONCLUSION

The MLCommons benchmark results could be improved for machine actionability and made more analysis-ready through the application of the FAIR Principles. Future work should include ways to constrain input of the system profiles, with potential use of defined ontologies for interoperability of log data. Further work is needed to improve data management practices of benchmark data —such as through the FAIR Principles— and to understand practical ways to incorporate power measurements into benchmark results. Tools —such as the capabilities developed for CloudMesh— help to quickly analyze energy demands. Through system profiling, one can uncover issues of scaling due to interconnect or programming constraints. Even with the current limitations of the benchmark results data, they provide insight for choosing hardware, software, and configurations, and lead to informed decisions about speed and power consumption tradeoffs.

The results of ML benchmarks are a trove of information for optimizing resource utilization and costs. This is especially true in academic research and any sector with limited resources or access. Even where funds are awarded for procurement, electricity and water consumption may be constrained in many instances. Cloud and HPC ML loads alike can be optimized through the application and analysis of HPC-style benchmarks. This can contribute to resource optimization to maximize science production.

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